

SELF-GLAZED CLINO-ENSTATITE BODIES

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Self glazed Clino-enstatite bodies have been obtained from talcum, and a glassy mass has been prepared from orthoclase and ferric oxide. The glossiness is due to accumulation of a thin layer of a ferruginous compound on the surface, the nature of which is identical with that of the cordierite bodies. The electrical characteristics of these are similar to those recorded for the improved bodies. It has been shown that the alkali metals in the body composition do not always affect the electric properties. The difference between the softening point and the densification temperature is also appreciable.

In recent years the mineral talc has come to be regarded as an important ingredient for high frequency ceramics, the production of which is rapidly increasing. Merits claimed for talc in such bodies have been stated to be that :

- (1) It is a cheap source of magnesia.
- (2) It imparts to the body a high resistance to thermal shock and a high electrical resistance at elevated temperatures.
- (3) It has a high specific heat and is resistant to acids (Hagar, *Ceram. Age*, 1933, 21, 74 ; King, *Ceram. Ind.*, 1935, 25, 70).

The electrical characteristics of the bodies prepared from talc depend, however, on the nature of the crystals formed and they are preferably called after the crystals that predominate in their structure (Rosenthal, "Porcelain and other Ceramic Insulating Materials", 1944, Vol. I, p. 251). A greater number of uniformly distributed clino-enstatite crystals occur per unit area in clino-enstatite bodies. These bodies possess a low power factor, average dielectric constant and a high mechanical strength.

Talc decomposes into enstatite and amorphous silica at about 1000°, and the inversion of the enstatite to clino-enstatite, $MgO \cdot SiO_2$, takes place between 1200° and 1300° with conversion of the amorphous silica into cristobalite (Ewell, Bunting and Geller, *J. Res., U. S. Nat. Bur. Standards*, 1935, 15, 551). On the other hand, it fuses suddenly at 1500° without showing any sign of softening and remains porous even at a temperature of a few degrees below its fusion point. Previously, for producing a dense and vitrified body from talc at a temperature well below its fusion point (at 1400°), addition like clay and feldspars was made. In improved clino-enstatite bodies, however, the use of feldspar has been given up in favour of fluxes like barium, strontium and magnesium carbonates. The glassy matrix formed by feldspar is supposed to prevent the clino-enstatite crystals from imparting their favourable dielectric characteristics (Rosenthal, *loc. cit.*).

Viewed qualitatively, the constituents of the vitreous phase is practically common in either case, only the improved body contains an alkaline earth oxide in place of K_2O .

The evil effect of feldspar may therefore be due either to the very presence of the alkali metal or to the manner in which it is placed in the vitreous mass. The literature shows that the type of alkali metal exerts some influence on the electrical properties. Thus, for bodies containing feldspar, orthoclase is used in preference to albite, as the latter has a detrimental effect on power loss (Newcomb, "Ceramic Whitewares", 1947, p. 258).

If the aforesaid suggestions be entertained, the electrical characteristics of clino-enstatite bodies containing feldspars of the bivalent metals should be similar to those of the improved bodies. This, naturally, suggests the use of anorthite or celsian, etc., being made. We have, however, preferred using a glassy mass, prepared from K-feldspar and iron oxide, as a substitute for orthoclase. This has been supposed to be a solid solution of iron analogue of anorthite, $\text{FeAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$ and iron orthoclase, KFeSi_3O_8 , and contains very little alkalis (Das Gupta and Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 582). There are two-fold reasons behind such preferential choice: Firstly, to use a cheap material containing very little alkali; secondly, to see if the new composition gives a self-glazed product. This latter aspect of the problem appears to be useful for manifold reasons. Thus, excepting for cordierite bodies (Thiess, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1943, 26, 99), no attempt has been made at preparing a self-glazed clino-enstatite body. Again, the 'Steatite' bodies are characterized by an extremely small thermal expansion. In actual practice it is very difficult to develop a glaze having an equally low thermal expansion. Lastly, complete densification was expected to take place at a relatively low temperature.

It has been found feasible to prepare a self-glazed clino-enstatite body using the aforesaid iron-feldspar as a flux. Compositions and other characteristics of only two of the best bodies (Nos. 6 and 7) have been included in the experimental portion. The electrical properties appear to be similar to those recorded for the improved bodies. To test if the presence of the alkali metals in the glassy matrix is always harmful, several trials were made from mixtures containing varying proportions of talc, China clay, potash feldspar, iron oxide, with or without a second colouring oxide. Satisfactory results could be obtained from some of these compositions. Their electrical characteristics too are almost identical with the body No. 7. This shows that the alkali metals are not always prejudicial.

Like self-glazed cordierite bodies (Das Gupta and Chatterjee, *ibid.*, 1951, 28, 611) the glossiness is due to accumulation of a thin layer of a ferruginous compound on the surface. In each case the surface of the fracture has the appearance of that of a normal insulator body. Under microscope, tiny specks of clino-enstatite crystals could be identified. The difference between the softening point and densification temperature is also appreciable. Necessary tests were performed only on those samples that appeared to be very satisfactory.

EXPERIMENTAL

Table I shows the ultimate analyses of the main ingredients used in the present investigation.

TABLE I

Substance.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	FeO.	MgO ₂ .	CaO.	MgO.	Alkalies.	Loss.
Talc	61.76%	0.10%	—	1.80%	2.06%	30.24%	—	4.08%
China clay	52.25	0.59	—	33.70	1.30	0.995	1.30%	9.50
Potash feldspar	64.01	0.71	0.13%	19.54	0.43	0.06	14.92	0.30
Synthetic iron feldspar	64.20	0.34	14.70	20.01	0.38	0.04	0.36	

* Total iron as Fe₂O₃.

Investigation has shown that the magnesium silica ratio in talc ranges from 1:1 to 4:3 and the water-content from 3 to over 7% (cf. Poshag and Wherry, *Amer. Min.* 1922, 7 No. 44, 167). From Table I, it is seen that the percentage composition agrees more closely with the formula, 3MgO.4SiO₂.H₂O. Besides, it is a lime-bearing talc from Jaipur, with a CaO content of 2.06% and is expected to give better results.

Sufficient quantity of talc was previously calcined at 1310° with a view to converting it mostly into clino-enstatite. This calcined mass was used for different trial experiments. The other ingredients were finely ground to pass 100 mesh sieve. In order to bring uniformity in composition, mixing was done in a pot mill for 48 hours. Trial pieces, either as blocks or as small tiles, were prepared by dry pressing. Perfectly dried samples were fired in a muffle furnace at 1300°-1310°. The maximum temperature was attained during 36 hours and a period of 10 hours was allowed for soaking. This was followed by the cooling process covering 48 hours. Table II shows only those compositions that yielded satisfactory results, and all particulars in respect of physical properties have been included in Table III.

TABLE II

Ingredients.	B o d y n u m b e r						
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
Calcined talc (%)	60	55	55	55	55	60	55
Potash feldspar (%)	38	42.5	36	34	33	—	—
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	2	2.5	3	2.5	2.5	—	—
China clay (%)	—	—	6	6.5	7	—	10
MnO ₂ (%)*	—	—	—	2	2.5	—	—
Synthetic iron feldspar (%)	—	—	—	—	—	40	35

Superficially, the proportions of talc and clay may appear to be low. The literature shows that the best value with regard to power factor is attained by a body (improved) consisting of talcum (80 parts), clay (20 parts) and barium carbonate (50 parts). This will show that there has not been appreciable departure from a tried composition.

TABLE III

Body No.	Hardness (Moh's scale)	Porosity.	Appearance.
1	7-8	Nil	Light brown, glossy
2	8	"	Brilliant light brown, glossy
3	8	"	Light creamish brown, glossy
4	7-8	"	Light chocolate, glossy
5	7-8	"	Matt creamish chocolate
6	8	"	Deep yellowish brown, glossy
7	8	"	Brilliant light yellowish brown

Comparatively, bodies (2), (3) and (7) appeared to us more perfect and, as such, these were examined under microscope (petrological). The report of such a test is shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

- No. 2 & 3. The minerals are fine grained. Tiny specks of clinoenstatite (needles showing oblique extinction and moderately high birefringence ; high refractive indices) are present.
- No. 7. Crystals are slightly more coarse grained than in (2) & (3). Larger portion of clinoenstatite ($Z\wedge C$ about 20°), high refractive indices and moderately high birefringence. A few turbid grains, comparatively fine in size, could not be specifically identified.

For mass production, the difference between the fusion point and the densification temperature needs be high. Table V gives information about fusion temperature, densification and porosity of bodies (2), (3) and (7). These bodies were heated to different temperatures for periods varying between 24 and 29 hours.

TABLE V

Temp.	Duration.	Density			Porosity		
		No. 2.	No. 3.	No. 7.	No. 2.	No. 3.	No. 7.
1180°	24 hrs.	2.63	2.66	2.68	28.8	30.6	29.4
1200°	24.5	2.67	2.69	2.71	22.2	26.5	26.7
1220°	25	2.69	2.74	2.75	19.3	21.2	22.03
1250°	26	2.72	2.78	2.79	6.7	13.3	16.3
1280°	27	2.76	2.81	2.87	1.83	2.84	3.1
1300°	27.5	2.77	2.85	2.92	0.002	0.004	0.03
1330°	28	2.78	2.88	2.94	Nil	Nil	Nil
1345°	28.5	2.78	2.88	2.94	"	"	"
1360°	29	2.80	2.90	2.96	"	"	"
1375°	29	Fuses	Fuses	2.98	—	—	"
1390°	29			Fuses	—	—	—

It is thus clear from the above table that there is a margin of at least $75^\circ-90^\circ$ for firing on a large scale.

The electrical characteristics of these bodies have been included in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Test.	No. 2.	No. 3.	No. 7	Remarks.
1. (a) Volume resistivity at 700°C (200 volts, 60 cycles) in ohms per cm.	2.6×10^4	2.9×10^4	3.3×10^4	During this determination a guard ring was used to eliminate surface current, thus allowing the true volume resistivity to be obtained.
(b) Do at 80°F	$> 1 \times 10^{11}$	$> 1 \times 10^{11}$	$> 1 \times 10^{11}$	
2. Dielectric constant (at 80°F), 60 cycles/sec	8.95	8.07	7.4	Thickness of each test piece was 1/4".
1,000 kC /sec	8.6	7.7	6.8	
3(a). Dielectric strength (60 cycles, test discs 1/4" thick) volt-per mil.	125	0	133	(a) The test discs were 3" diam, and 1/4" thick. They were immersed in oil at 80°F. Voltage at 60 cycles per sec. was increased from zero at the rate of 1.0 kV./sec. until breakdown occurred.
(b) For test discs 6" x 6" x 1/8" thick	132	138	145	

Table VI shows that excepting the values for dielectric strength, the other values are in close agreement with those recorded for improved clino-enstatite bodies. It is expected to bring about further improvements in this direction and this will form the subject matter for a future communication.

CONCLUSION

It is quite feasible to prepare self-glazed bodies from talc, China clay, and potash feldspar or its iron counterpart having clino-enstatite crystals.

These bodies mature at 1300°, and this is lower than the temperature, ordinarily, needed for firing improved clino-enstatite bodies (1400°).

The ingredients are relatively cheap.

For improved bodies, the use of potash feldspar is not always prejudicial.

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